

IMPACTS OF INVESTMENTS ON REGIONAL AND LOCAL DEVELOPMENT; THE CASE OF (SEOUL, SOUTH KOREA)

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Abstract: This article aims to present the impact of investment on a local and regional scale in Seoul in South Korea. The questionnaire survey approach was undertaken to get the perspectives of the related community members on the impact of technology in the regions of Seoul. As per the survey, the developments within the technology field increase the technical capabilities of the region and the betterment of future developments, increase the jobs and offer a platform for other regions.

Keywords: Investment, technologies, Foreign Direct Investment (FDI), capitalizing, innovation.

Introduction:

From the beginning of the innovation of technology, Seoul (South Korea) has been among the leading industries. The technology, smartphones, and innovative projects industry has led South Korea among the leading market contenders on the innovation index. According to Bloomberg's 2020 Innovation Index, South Korea is on 11th place out of the 129 countries (Roukanas, 2021). The continuous research and development approach taken within South Korea has opened numerous doors for success in the region; the most common one is the leading electronics and smartphone company Samsung in Seoul (Kim, 1997). The government's interests in the technology field in South Korea have led to further developments. South Korea is currently at a pivotal point. The nation has succeeded in developing into a technologically advanced economic powerhouse, thanks mainly to large conglomerates producing software and hardware. The setting is beginning to alter. The number of startups is rising, and they have an enormous effect on the marketplace (Campbell, 2012). Foreigners encounter

barriers to entry into the South Korean market due to mindsets, cultural differences, and the language, even though many other characteristics make it appealing.

Fig-1. Korea is leading in the technology and innovation field

The capital of the technology hub of South Korea is Seoul, which resides in the world's most extensive smartphone and electronics manufacturing facility Samsung. Since the Korean war, Seoul has served as the economic hub for the country (Mahlich & Pascha, 2007). They are developing the population with education and enhancing their skillset towards perfectionism in the technologies such as televisions, smartphones, semiconductors, and electronic devices. Seoul is well known for the developments in technology, and further developments are in the pipeline as well.

Fig-2. Korea's investment resources in technology

They invest in virtual industries such as the metaverse project, 6G wireless network, and artificial intelligence. Towards the research and development facilities in Seoul, the government is investing in innovation within the technology department, for which subsidies are being given to the research facilities to promote technological innovation within the region. South Korea is to invest about USD 5.3 billion in technology and science research (Koojaroenprasit, 2012).

Technology investments in Seoul have developed the research and development facilities for innovation in the field.

Fig-3. The developments within the city of Seoul (Korea)

Today, Korea provides developing nations with development expertise that serves as an example for sustainability, providing improved infrastructure and services to enhance the lives of the populace, and making the shift to a thriving knowledge economy. Korea's official development aid budget has increased steadily, reaching 2.22 billion USD in 2020, or 0.14 percent of GNI. The country has also promised to increase its ODA by two times by 2030 from 2019.

Fig-4 Investments within the research and development sector in Seoul

Research on the importance of investments in a region

Innovation plays a significant role in the development of the whole region and in establishing the region's economic growth. The same approach is undertaken in Seoul by investing a significant budget towards ICT and science research and development sectors. South Korea is developing the facilities for artificial intelligence, for which in the fiscal 2022 budget, there is an investment of about \$3 billion in the AI field, which will enhance the capabilities in the different services related to AI (Gestrin, 2019).

	South Korea	United States	Japan	China
Ease of Doing Business Rank	4	6	34	78
Starting a Business	9	49	106	93
Getting Electricity	2	49	17	98
Getting Credit	55	2	77	68
Trading across Borders	33	36	51	97
Enforcing Contracts	1	16	51	5
Resolving Insolvency	5	3	1	56

SOURCE: World Bank

2018 World Bank Doing Business Rankings

Semiconductors are among the critical industries for Seoul and Korea together. As per the country's authorities, the semiconductor trades are about 20.2% of the real exports, and Seoul is the hub of the leading memory chip manufacturer Samsung Electronics. An investment of about \$1.5 billion will be added for further industry development. Cloud computing is also among the leading services offered by the region, and this marketplace is growing from \$2.85 billion in 2021 to \$3.1 billion in 2022. The government and the responsible authorities are planning to invest around \$750 million for future innovation within the cloud computing industry in Seoul.

Fig-5. The scale of investment in the tech industry and services in Seoul

Conclusion

Investments in technology innovation in the Seoul region lead to the economy's development and enhance the research and development facilities. Investments in the technology field can be observed from different aspects; however, the significant impact it has is on the economic development in the region, increasing the exports through products and related services. Innovation opens the gate for foreign investors to consider investing within the region towards the innovation in technology to improve life quality, reduce unemployment and develop the region and the communities.

Fig-6. *Developments leading towards innovation in Seoul*

References

1. Campbell, J. R. (2012). Building an IT Economy: South Korean Science and Technology Policy. *Issues in Technology Innovation*, 19, 1–9. http://english.mest.go.kr/web/1715/site/contents/en/en_0217.jsp;
2. Gestrin, M. (2019). The contribution of international business investment to the Sustainable Development Goals. *The Contribution of International Business Investment to the Sustainable Development Goals: Key Actors and Recent Trends*, OECD, Paris. www.oecd.org/investment/The-contribution-of-international-business-investment-to-the-sustainable-
3. Kim, Y.-S. (1997). TECHNOLOGY AND DEVELOPMENT: Impact of Technology on the Korean Economy. *Korea Journal of Population and Development*, 26(2), 101–120. <http://www.jstor.org/stable/43783504>
4. Koojaroenprasit, S. (2012). The impact of foreign direct investment on economic growth: A case study of South Korea. *International Journal of Business and Social Science*, 3(21), 8–19. www.ijbssnet.com
5. Mahlich, J., & Pascha, W. (2007). *Innovation and technology in Korea: Challenges of a newly advanced economy*. <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-7908-1914-4>
6. Roukanas, S. (2021). *Measuring Innovation of Countries*. 2021, 157–189. <https://doi.org/10.18502/kss.v5i9.9892>